

EXAMINING JOB-RELATED STRESS AND ITS IMPACT ON TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ABUJA

Benjamin Michael Johnson

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Administration, The University of America, Curacao,
Willemstad, Curacao, United Kingdom of Netherlands

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14922785

Abstract:

The study examines Job related stress and teachers' performance in some selected Secondary Schools in Abuja – Nigeria. A survey research method was used for the study. The primary data were generated through the instrument of questionnaire while secondary materials were sourced from past studies. Three research questions, objectives and hypotheses were formulated for the study. The population of the study was 500 employees of the selected secondary school in Abuja, out of which 222 respondents were selected and administered copies of questionnaire. The technique for data analysis was simple percentage statistical. The findings from the analysis revealed that job stress generally negatively affects the performance of employees in the selected secondary schools in Abuja. Three sources of job stress were identified: workload stress, working facilities stress and poor working condition. Findings showed that each of the sources has significant impact on teachers' performance. The study therefore, recommended among others, that all teachers in the selected secondary schools in Abuja should be given a commensurable work schedule as this will go a long way to reducing stress on the teaching staff of the selected secondary schools in Abuja and subsequently enhance their performance. In addition, the selected secondary schools in Abuja should provide appropriate work facilities and infrastructure to enable learning and a friendly working environment, which may lead to higher job performance among teachers.

Keywords: Job, Stress, Teachers, Performance

Introduction 1.1 Background of the Study

Stress is commonly associated with a specific incident or occurrence that one undergoes at a point in time. Usually, stress is used to refer to an emotional strain at a certain point of an experience. Stress is the way people react to changes, events, and situations in their lives, both physically and mentally. People feel stress in a variety of ways and for a variety of reasons. The reaction is determined by how one perceives an event or scenario. When one has a negative perspective on a situation, he or she is likely to feel distressed, overwhelmed, oppressed, or out of control. The more common form of stress is distress; evidence is mounting that the psychosocial environment in which people work affects both job performance and job satisfaction (Clements-Croome, 2013; Shaw & Readon, 2014). Workers' jobs in modern office buildings are becoming increasingly complex and reliant on sophisticated

technology, and corporations whose occupancy costs are rising often strive to lower them without negatively impacting the workers. Such workspace selections are intended to make an investment in employees' quality of life, with the notion that measurable productivity benefits will ensue. Studies are finding more and more connections between employee health and the psychosocial environment at work, such as the amount of pressure from home and pressure from a superior officer, as well as the air quality, ergonomic furniture and lighting.

Stress may however be seen as having two dimensions. "First, there is experiential aspect, that leads to psychological state of body system distress or tension where an individual may have an unpleasant feeling. Then there is physiological aspect which can be perceived as in threatening situation the body responded with a "fight or flight"" syndrome. Stress is the general term applied to the pressure people felt in life. As a result of these pressures, employees develop various symptoms of stress that can harm their job performance. Stress is considered as an „arousal reaction (positive or negative) to some job personal related stimulus. " The stimulus that causes stress is called a stressor. Stress is positive if it enables a person to perform or excel in a given situation or event. It is negative if there is excessive amount of stress that causes an individual to reduce performance. In another view Thoits, (2010) explained stress in terms of these three related concepts: Anxiety, Conflicts and Frustration. It is almost impossible to isolate these three concepts from stress. In many ways, teachers" stress has not much difference from other forms of stress.

Teaching has conventionally been considered as a low-stress profession, but the situation has been somersaulted during these last three decades Olivier and Venter (2003). Many studies, example Bakare (2005) have revealed that teaching is the most stressful profession/job comparing to other professions/jobs. The majority of current research on workplace stress focuses on psychosocial factors that influence job performance, strain, and employee health. The physical environment is a factor in certain theoretical models of workplace stress (Klitzman & Stellman, 2018). However, much of the research relating to physical environmental elements refer to the physical dimensions of the tasks being performed rather than features of the psychosocial space in which they are conducted. Most research on job stress and other aspects of workplace stress do not look at the growing amount of work on the psychology of the workplace environment.

Teaching staff is primarily responsible for the academic activities of any institution such as research and teaching (Fatma, 2003). The primary functions of teaching and research determine high satisfaction with the facilities which exist to enable them to carry out their tasks satisfactorily. However, in the current secondary schools" scenario, the teachers" workloads are increasing to encompass not only teaching and research but also fulfilling administrative demands.

Work related stress is one of the most important and rapidly growing factors affecting ones" health. According to "Stress in America: The State of Our Nation Report 2017" (APA, 2017) the increase on the percentage of

Americans experiencing at least one symptom of stress (i.e. feeling nervous, anger, fatigue) in the past month reached to 75 which was 71 in 2016. Similarly, Health and Safety Executive (HSE) (2017) reports, that stress, depression or anxiety accounts for the 40 percent of the total work-related ill health cases in Britain. According to APA (2017), money and work are the top stressors among Americans, by considering the results of surveys being conducted more than a decade. There are numerous studies all over the world suggesting similar results too. For example, work related stress can cause psychological (such as; depression, anxiety, illogical thinking and decision making and so on) and physical problems (such as; headache, muscle-skeleton disorders, high blood pressure and even in extreme cases heart attack). In fact, work related stress affects people negatively in any way (Kotteeswari & Sharief, 2014). For that reason, increasing our insights on work stress can be beneficial for coping with the negative effects of stress.

Stress has a significant negative impact on employees' physical, emotional and behavioral as well as economic implications to organizations, and the nation as a whole. Stressed workers are prone to diseases like hypertension, cardiovascular disease, depression, etc. with their associated huge medical bills. Also, the employee is more likely to be unhealthy, poorly motivated, less productive and less safe at work" (ILO, 2016).

Stress has become a big problem in today's workplace. Work overload, role conflict, lack of task autonomy, job instability, and long hours of work, changes in duty, timetable, tight deadlines, and poor relationships with colleagues are some of the causes (Kamalak, Umati & Ambika, 2013). Employees in today's jobs are subjected to a variety of forms of stress. Stress is a complicated and dynamic term that has an impact on the entire performance of an organization's workforce. When the organization's most valuable assets go through stressful situations, it can cause them to do bad things at work, like miss days, be late, and be less productive overall (Arbabisarjon, Ajdari, Omeidi, and Jalalinejad, 2013).

According to Mullins (2017), one of the most important issues confronting European businesses is stress, which is a major source of negative influence on the quality of work-life and employee performance. According to the Health and Safety Executive (HSE), high levels of stress can lead to mental and physical health problems such as depression, neurological breakdown, and other heart-related illnesses. In other words, occupational stress has a substantial impact on job satisfaction and organizational commitment, and it can contribute to excessive absenteeism and employee turnover. Khatibi, Asadi, and Hamidi (2019) say that job stress and organizational commitment go in opposite directions.

The secondary school is an academic institution that trains a high-level workforce for the country's development, and new technological developments have blurred the line between work and life outside of work to the point where labor extends beyond the officially authorized hours. As a result, employees are increasingly recognizing that work is substantially interfering with their personal lives, and they are dissatisfied with the development

because it is a major source of work stress. In light of the foregoing, the study investigates the effects of job-related stress on teachers' performance in selected secondary schools in Abuja.

Stress has significant impact on company and people performance and it terribly affects health of employees (Mimura and Griffiths, 2003 in Shah et al, 2012). The studies conducted in western countries have shown that the sources of stress that we name as Occupational Stress Inducers (OSI) in this study are negatively related to well-being and job satisfaction of employees. (Robertson, Cooper, & Williams, 1990). Shah et al. (2012) in their study on impact of stress on employee performance among teaching faculty, found a negative relationship between organizational structure and employee efficiency while rewards were found to be positively correlated to employee efficiency as expected. Rubina et al. (2008) too found a negative relationship between job stress and job performance. However, the male employees were found to be affected more than their female counter parts. Munir and Islam (2011) tested relationship between work stressors like role ambiguity, workload pressure, home-work interface, performance pressure, relationship with others and role conflicts on one side and job performance on the other with motivation as mediator and found that "role conflict" and "role ambiguity" have a positive relation with stressors against the common notion while the relationship is found to be negative between other stressors and job performance. Imrab et al. (2013) found that stress is responsible for decreasing the performance of bank employees.

Ahmed & Ramzan (2013) too found a negative correlation between stress and job performance i.e. as the stress increases the job performance goes down and vice-a-versa. Usman Ali et al. (2014) found that workload, role conflict, and inadequate monetary reward are the prime reasons of causing stress in employees that leads to reduced employee efficiency. Designer (2003) suggested that different aspects of employee job performance that are likely to be affected by stress include productivity, job satisfaction / morale, absenteeism, decision making abilities, accuracy, creativity, attention to personal appearance, organizational skills, courtesy cooperation, initiative, reliability, alertness, perseverance and tardiness. It is against this background that this study investigates job-related stress and teachers' performance in some selected secondary schools in Abuja – Nigeria

1.2 Aims and Objectives

The main objective of this study was to describe work-related stress and its eventual relationship with job performance of teachers working in some selected Secondary Schools of Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, while, other specific objectives were to:

- i. Examine the effect of workload stress on teachers' resource management of the selected secondary schools in Abuja.
- ii. Determine the effect of work facility stress on teachers' self-development in the selected secondary schools in Abuja
- iii. Ascertain the extent work conditions stress affect teachers' absenteeism at selected secondary schools in Abuja.

1.3 Research Questions

The under listed research questions guided this study.

- i. To what extent has workload stress affected teachers' performance in selected secondary schools in Abuja?
- ii. What is the effect of work facility stress on teachers' performance in selected secondary schools in Abuja?
- iii. To what extent does work condition stress affect teachers' performance in selected secondary schools in Abuja?

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

For the purpose of this study, the survey and documentary research design methods were adopted. It involves using questionnaires to collect data from the respondents and reviewing relevant documents to complement the questionnaire. This method was chosen because it is quick and uses few resources. This study adopted the survey research design approach in its investigation. A survey design was adopted because it covers the entire population using the representative sample of the study. It measured a relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling either of them. It also measured the statistically significant relationship between two variables that would predict one variable using information available on another variable. The descriptive survey design is relevant to this study because it assists the researcher to explore the relationship between an independent variable (stress) and a dependent variable (teachers' performance). This study therefore focused on getting information on job-related stress and teachers' performance in some selected Secondary Schools in Abuja.

3.2 Area of Study

Federal Government Boys College was founded in 1999. It is the only federal college for boys in the whole capital city. Situated in the Garki district, it has over two hundred certified teachers and over 1,700 students. It is a boarding school that also accommodates day students. Unlike the lackadaisical trend in some government schools in the country, the complete tutoring and education of the students is on the priority list of the school. That is why the students are known for acing their examinations, especially the ones organized by WASSCE and NECO. Also, Federal Government College in the Kwali area council is a mixed-boarding school. The area where the school is situated used to be densely populated, but, recently, mass relocation from other parts of the city has made the Kwali area council fit to be called an urban area due to the changes in the environment, new businesses cropping up every day, and infrastructure. Federal Government College, Kwali, Abuja, is one of the co-educational Unity Colleges in the country. It was established on the 6th of January, 1984, with an intake of junior secondary one (JS 1) only. The College is located at Kwali town in the Kwali Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory, 13 kilometers out of Gwagwalada, along Kaduna-Lokoja Road, Kwali, 68 kilometers south-west of Abuja Capital City and 48 kilometers south of Suleja. The Federal Government Academy is also known as Suleja Academy. It

was founded in 1986 by the Federal Government under the Babangida regime. Unlike other secondary schools in the country, it is a special school for children who are highly intelligent. The school is well equipped, accommodating both male and female students trained by qualified teachers. Getting one's ward admitted into the school isn't a walk in the park. Starting with the processing fees of about 5, 000, a child seeking admission into Junior Class One must be 11 years or older. The school frowns at taking in younger children under 11 years old, regardless of how brilliant they are. The Federal Government College in Rubochi, Kuje, was founded in April, 2000. It is a boarding school, running a very good curriculum, with alumni all over the world. Similarly, Federal Government Girls College, Abaji was Founded and commissioned in 1982 in the Abaji Local Government Area, along

Abaji–Toto Road, Abaji FCT Abuja. Government Girls Secondary School Abaji is one of the tops 10 government senior secondary schools in Abuja. Also, Federal Government Girls College in Abaji is a boarding school for girls only, situated in Abaji area council, in the capital city. Abaji is known as the land of the Egbira, Ganagana, and Hausa people. In another development,

Federal Government Girls College, Bwari was also used and The Federal Government Girls" College, Bwari-Abuja, came into being on January 15th, 1984 to meet the demand for girl-child education in the FCT, the middle belt and the country at large. It was the 41st Unity College to be established in the country and the second in the Federal Capital Territory after Kwali. It is a boarding school that took off with 43 students and 8 teaching and 10 non-teaching staff. Also, Army Day Secondary School, Maitama was

Founded in 1992, Army Day Secondary School in Maitama is one of the top 10 government senior secondary schools in Abuja. It is located within the Municipal Local Government Area, particularly in Mambilla Barrack, Maitama, Abuja. The manner of inculcating discipline and success results makes the public senior secondary one of the first choices of parents around Abuja. Government Secondary School Wuse is located on Abidjan Street, Zone 3, Wuse, FCT Abuja. It was established around 1987 in the Municipal Local Government Area. It is ranked as one of the top ten government senior secondary schools in Abuja. And Government Day Secondary School, Dutse Alhaji, FCT Abuja, Government Day Secondary School, Dutse Alhaji, was established in 2008 in Bwari Local Government Area. It is one of the most successfully recognized public senior secondary schools in the city of Abuja, conforming to the Universal Basic Education protocols and requirements for the training of young children.

3.3 Sources of Data

Given the empirical nature of the study, primary data was heavily relied upon

3.3.1 Primary Source

The source data collection for this study was the use of questionnaire delivered to the selected principals, vice principals, teachers and students of the selected schools within the six area councils of Abuja.

3.3.2 Secondary Source

The source data collection for this study was the use of questionnaire delivered to the selected principals, vice principals, teachers and students of the selected schools within the six area councils of Abuja.

3.4 Population of study

A population of study according to Onwumere (2015) comprises of all elements: subjects and perhaps observations in relation to a particular phenomenon. For the purpose of this study, the population of the study includes 10 principals, 20 vice principals (academic and administration), 10 principals, 20 vice principals (academic and administration), 220 teachers, and 250 senior secondary school students from the selected schools; Federal Government Boys' College; Federal Government Academy; Federal Government College, Kwali; Federal Government College,

Rubochi; Federal Government Girls College, Abaji; International Community School, Asokoro;

Federal Government Girls College, Bwari; Army Day Secondary School, Maitama; Government Secondary School Wuse; Government Day Secondary School Dutse Alhaji; thus, making a total of 500 respondents for the study.

3.5 Sampling Procedure (Sampling Method & Sample Size Determination)

In this study, purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique, was adopted. This means the procedure of selection was deliberately carried out by the researcher. The study employed purposive sampling techniques whereby the researcher issued questionnaires to those directly involved in the study. The study used a purposive sample to choose a sample of respondents based on information about the study and the population. The sample's schools were chosen based on the study's objective. sample size is referred to as a certain number of precisely defined parts of the population that together represents the total element under study. Out of the five hundred respondents, a sample size of 222 respondents were selected for the study, which was a fair representation of the total subject. The sample size was determine using the Taro Yamane (1964) formula

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

Given the empirical nature of the study, primary data was heavily relied upon. The source data collection for this study was the use of questionnaire delivered to the selected principals, vice principals, teachers and students of the selected schools within the six area councils of Abuja. Also, the secondary sources of data collection were obtained through gazette, official document from the selected schools, textbooks from library, paper presentation in conferences and seminars, different websites on the internet and unpublished project reports.

3.7 Reliability of Instrument

The reliability for using the survey method in this research is that it is one of the appropriate methods for gathering large amounts of information. It can also allow the subjects being surveyed to remain anonymous and help to

eliminate bias in the interpretation of results. Its major attractions are: its relatively low cost considering the fact that useful information was collected about a large number of people from a relatively small number (representative); it will be easy to generalize the findings to a larger population once representativeness of the sample is assured; and the flexibility of the survey means that a variety of data collection instruments (observations, interviews, questionnaires) could be used. This allows one instrument to serve as a check on the other

3.8 Validity of the instrument

Validity refers to the degree to which an instrument accurately measures what it intends to measure. Therefore, construct and content validity were used in the study. The structured questionnaire items were submitted to experts, research supervisors, and professors with expert knowledge in the field to confirm the material's content validity. The study used confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to demonstrate the validity of the construct. The CFA allows the researcher to verify the factor structure or loading of a set of observed variables. CFA was used to determine the composite reliability to measure internal consistency in scale items and discriminant validity of the research instrument to test whether measurements that are not supposed to be related are unrelated. This helped to confirm if the questionnaire developed for this study is valid for decision- makings. At the same time discriminant validity was also checked.

3.9 Data Analysis Approach/Method

For the purpose of this study, the descriptive method of data analysis was used. The descriptive statistics was used to present the data. Descriptive statistics are frequency tables, figures, and charts. The data collected from respondents was analyzed using inferential statistics. Averages mean score was used to test the hypothesis. This study used the following decision rule to accept or reject the hypothesis: When the weighted average means score is equal to 2.50 and above, null hypothesis is Rejected and alternative hypothesis Accepted. Also, the weighted average means score is less than 2.50 and below null hypothesis is Accepted and alternative Rejected. The analysis was represented in tabular form for easy understanding of its content, the number of respondents, and the corresponding percentage. In addition to this, the data collected was presented in tables, using absolute figures and their corresponding percentages, capable of self-explanation and further analysis.

4.0 Results and Analysis

Table 4.1 Frequency Of Respondent's responses on the extent has workload affected teachers' performance in the selected Secondary Schools in Abuja

Items	Agree	Disagree	undecided
› what extent has workload affected teachers' performance in the selected Secondary Schools in Abuja?	107(53.5%)	64(32.0%)	29(14.5%)
› determine the number of subjects taught affects the quality of teaching delivery	135(67.5%)	58(29%)	7(3.5%)
› determine the number of students attended to affect quality of teaching	95(47.5%)	63(31.5%)	42(21%)
The extent number of examination script and continuous assessment scripts attended to affect objective assessment of student's performance	117(58.5%)	55(27.5%)	28(14%)

Table 4.1 contain the Frequency of Respondent's responses on the extent has workload affected teachers' performance in the selected Secondary Schools in Abuja. The response on whether teacher experience workload stress revealed that 107 representing 53.5% of the respondents agreed while 64 representing 32% of the respondents disagreed and 29 representing 14.5% of the respondents were undecided about the question. Response on whether number of subjects taught affect quality of lecture delivery revealed 135 representing 67.5% of the respondents agreed while 58 representing 29% of the respondents disagreed and 7 representing 3.5% of the respondents were undecided. Also, Responses on whether number of students attended to affect quality of teaching, revealed that 95 representing 47.5% of the respondents agreed while 63 representing 31.5% of the respondents disagreed and 42 representing 21% of the respondents were undecided. Responses on whether number of examination script and continuous assessment scripts attended to affect objective assessment of student's performance, revealed 117 representing 58.5% of the respondents agreed while 55 representing 27.5% of the respondents disagreed and 25 representing 14% of the respondents were undecided.

Objective Two:

Table 4.2 Frequency of Respondent's responses on the effect of work facility on teachers' performance in the selected Secondary Schools in Abuja

Items	Agree	Disagree	undecided
To extent the inadequate work facilities affect employee performance	148(74%)	41(20.5%)	11(5.5%)
To extent insufficient office accommodation promotes absenteeism of employee from work	133(66.5%)	52(26%)	15(7.5%)
How lack of teaching aids affects quality delivery of lessons	146(73%)	48(24%)	6(3%)
To extent the lack of office infrastructure affects hours spent in office	133(66.5%)	46(23%)	21(10.5%)

Table 4.2 contains the frequency of respondent's responses on the effect of work facility on teachers' performance in the selected secondary schools in Abuja. The respondents were asked whether inadequate work facilities affect employee performance, the data obtained revealed that 148 representing 74% of the respondents agreed while 41 representing 20.5% of the respondents disagreed and 11 representing 5.5% of the respondents were undecided. Responses on whether insufficient office accommodation brings about absenteeism, revealed that 133 representing 66.5% of the respondents agreed while 52 representing 26% of the respondents disagreed and 15 representing 7.5% of the respondents were undecided. Responses on whether lack of teaching aids affects quality delivery of lessons revealed 146 representing 73% of the respondents agreed while 48 representing 24% of the respondents disagreed and 6 representing 3% of the respondents were undecided and responses on whether lack of office infrastructure affects hours spent in the office, revealed 133 representing 66.5% of the respondents agreed while 46 representing 23% of the respondents disagreed and 21 representing 10.5% of the respondents were undecided.

Research Question Three: To what extent does work condition affect teachers' performance in the selected Secondary Schools in Abuja?

Table 4.3: Frequency Of Respondent's responses on the effect of work facility on teachers' performance in the selected Secondary Schools in Abuja

Items	Agree	Disagree	undecided
to the extent unfavorable work conditions affect teacher's performance	198(99%)	0(0%)	2(1%)
How low remunerations bring about poor attitude to work	152(76%)	41(20.5%)	7(3.5%)
to the extent poor implementation of promotion brings about low morale of employees	122(61%)	60(34.5%)	9(4.5%)
How poor staff development brought about low employees' output	117(58.5%)	59(29.5%)	24(12%)

Table 4.3 contain the frequency of respondent's responses on the effect of work facility on teachers' performance in the selected secondary schools in Abuja. The responses on whether unfavorable work conditions affect employee performance revealed 198 representing 99% of the respondents agreed while 0 representing 0% of the respondents disagreed and 2 representing 1% of the respondents were undecided. The data obtained revealed that 152 representing 76% of the respondents agreed that low remunerations bring about poor attitude to work while 41 representing 20.5% of the respondents disagreed and 7 representing 3.5% of the respondents were undecided as regard the question. The data obtained revealed that 122 representing 61% of the respondents agreed poor implementation of promotion brings about lowered morale of employees while 69 representing 34.5% of the respondents disagreed and 9 representing 4.5% of the respondents were undecided. The data obtained revealed that 117 representing 58.5% of the respondents agreed poor staff development bring about low output while 59 representing 29.5% of the respondents disagreed and 24 representing 12% of the respondents were undecided.

4.2 Test of Hypothesis I

H₀₁: Workload stress has no significant effect on the teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja.

The analyzes the effect on the teachers' performance of selected secondary schools in Abuja were computed using the critical value of weighted means score and the result is shown in table 4.5 below

Table 4.4: Calculation of Critical Value of Weighted Means Score

Variable	Agreed	Disagreed	Undecided	Total No of Respondents/Score	Weighted Mean
Responses	107	64	29	200	478/200
Grading	3	2	1	-	-
Total Value	321	128	29	478/200	2.39
Decision	-	-	-	-	Rejected

Source: Research Data, 2022

Table above shows the result of the calculated value of weighted means score at 2.39. This means that, the calculated value is not scientifically significant because, it is less than 2.50. We will therefore accept the research hypothesis which states that, workload stress has no significant effect on the teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja and reject alternative hypothesis which shows that, workload stress has effect on the teachers' performance of selected secondary schools in Abuja. This means that, teachers of the selected secondary schools in Abuja faced workload stress which does not affect their performance.

H02: Working facilities has no significant effect on teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja.

The analyses the effect of working facilities on teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja were computed using the critical value of weighted means score and the result is shown in table 4.5 below

Table 4.5: Calculation of Critical Value of Weighted Means Score

Variable	Agreed	Disagreed	Undecided	Total No. of Respondents/score	Weighted Mean
Responses	148	41	11	200	⁴⁴⁶ / ₁₆₆
Grading	3	2	1	-	-
Total Value	444	82	11	537/200	2.68
Decision	-	-	-	-	Accepted

Source: Research Data, 2022

Table above show the result of the calculated value of weighted means score at 2.68. This means that, the calculated value is scientifically significant at 2.68 because, it is greater than 2.50. We will therefore reject the research hypothesis which stated that, working facilities has no significant effect on teachers' performance of selected secondary schools in Abuja and accept alternative hypothesis which shows that, there is significant

relationship between working facilities and teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja. This means that, working facilities has significant effect on the performance of teachers in the selected secondary schools in Abuja.

H0₃: Work condition has no significant effect on teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja.

The analyzed the extent to working condition affects teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja were computed using the Critical Value of Weighted Means Score and the results are shown in table 4.6

Table 4.20: Calculation of Critical Value of Weighted Means Score

Variable	Agreed	Disagreed	Undecided	Total No of Respondents/Score	Weighted Mean
Responses	198	0	2	200	⁵⁹⁶ / ₂₀₀
Grading	3	2	1	-	-
Total Value	594	0	2	⁵⁹⁶ / ₂₀₀	2.98
Decision	-	-	-	-	Accepted

Source: Research Data, 2022

Table above shows the result of the calculated value of weighted means score at 2.98. This means that, the calculated value is scientifically significant at 2.98 because, it is more than 2.50. We will therefore reject the research hypothesis, which states that work condition has no significant effect on teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja and accept the alternative hypothesis, which shows that work condition has effect on teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja. This means that, working conditions has significant effect on teachers' performance of selected secondary schools in Abuja.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The objective of this study was to examine the impact of stress on teachers' performance of selected secondary schools in Abuja and how significant other variables such as workload stress, working facilities, and work conditions have effect on teachers' performance of selected secondary schools in Abuja. The discussion of findings is structured in a way that it can address the research objectives.

Effect of workload on teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja

From the data presented, the survey participants opined that teacher of selected the secondary schools in Abuja face workload stress which affects their performance; this was demonstrated in table 4.18. This means that employees' performance is strongly related to the workload assigned. This finding collaborates with that of Joseph (2017) whose findings showed that excess workload of administrative responsibilities lowers job efficiency of

non-academic staff. Ademola, Clara and Babalola (2015) whose result revealed that job-stress dimensions independently and jointly influenced job performance adversely. Salami, Ojokuku, Ilesanmi, (2010) findings showed that job stress brought about subjective effects such as fear, anger and anxiety among Nigerian managers resulting in poor concentration, mental block and poor decision-making skills. But differs with Swaminathan & Rajkumar (2013) whose study indicates that, an optimum level in which every individual can perform with his full capacity and identified three conditions responsible for work stress they are; Role overload, Role self-distance, Role stagnation. This study established that workload is a big concern to employees" of Nasarawa State University hence, employees experienced pressure due to work overload.

Effect of work facility on teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja

The data obtained in table 4.6 above analyses the effect of working facilities on employees" performance in the selected secondary schools in Abuja. The data obtained in table 4.5 showed that inadequate work facilities affect employees" performance, hence insufficient office accommodation and space bring about absenteeism and lack of teaching and working tools affect quality of teaching delivered and timely delivery of responsibilities, the study further revealed that insufficient infrastructures affect hours spent in office. The finding corroborates the study of Edem, Akpan and Pepple (2017) whose finding revealed worker's productivity and performance can decrease due to poorly planned workplace environment and facilities as this adversely affects their morale and may give rise to poor motivation and no job satisfaction. Again, Khaled and Haneen (2017) whose findings revealed that the situational constrains such as inadequate computers, internet facilities, noise, office furniture, and ventilation and light, are the major work environment conditions that have negative impact on job performance and should gain more attention. The finding showed that working facilities plays a vital role in employees" performance.

To what extent do work conditions affect teachers' performance of the selected secondary schools in Abuja

Table 4.20 above analyses the extent working conditions affect employees" performance in the selected secondary schools in Abuja. The result revealed that unfavorable work conditions affect employees" performance and that low remunerations of employee brings about poor attitude to work, the study revealed that poor implementation of promotion also lowers employee morale and poor staff development bring about low output and quality of service. This finding is in line with Nduku, Mwenda, and Anita (2021) who explored the effects of working conditions on the performance of employees of Kenya Commercial Bank and found out that Working conditions have a positive effect on the performance of employee. Ekundayo (2018) investigates the relationship between motivation and the level of employee performance as applied to some selected insurance companies in Lagos. The findings revealed that motivation was the major factor that affected employee performance. Furthermore, the study showed a direct strong and positive relationship between motivation of employees and their performance.

5.2 Conclusion

Keeping in view the important role of teaching profession in economic and social development of a country, the concept of teachers' performance has achieved a strategic significance. The performance of a teacher is affected by intra as well as extra organizational factors, which act as impediments to normal routine functioning of teachers. Once the routine functioning of teachers is disrupted, then teachers develop feelings of exhaustion and frustration, and if the disrupted situation persists then negative dysfunctional feelings hit the teachers, which can be termed as stress, which is a reaction to the unwanted environmental stressors. Teachers under stress cannot perform well. Their job satisfaction and motivation levels are decreased and they show unwanted behaviors like absenteeism, mistakes during work and violence at work. This study examined the impact of stress on teachers' performance of some selected secondary schools in Abuja. High workload, work facilities and work condition of teachers' performance. It is evident that impact of high work overload and work facilities related stress have affected teachers' performance negatively among the selected secondary schools in Abuja. The study concludes that, stress has negative impact on teachers' performance. Workload, work facilities, work condition and job content have different results and relationship with teachers' performance in the selected secondary schools in Abuja. Stress led to negative consequences in the working environment so it is essential to reduce stress from workplace.

5.3 Recommendations

The study recommends that,

- i. All teachers in the selected secondary schools in Abuja should be given commensurable work schedule as this will go a long way to reduce stress on teaching staff of the selected secondary schools in Abuja and subsequently enhanced their performance.
- ii. The selected secondary schools in Abuja should make effort to provide appropriate work facilities and infrastructure in order to have enabling learning and friendly working environment, which may lead to higher job performance among teachers.
- iii. The selected secondary schools in Abuja should provide adequate work conditions for the teachers' as it will enhance performance, because insufficient office accommodation and space bring about absenteeism, lack of teaching and working tools affect quality of teaching delivered and timely delivery of responsibilities, thus, insufficient infrastructures affect hours spent in office.

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